

LICOCHALCONE A, EGFR REVIEW

TITLE : Licochalcone A as a promising natural inhibitor of EGFR : A mini review with computational insights

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ABSTRACT : Brain tumor are among the most aggressive and challenging diseases to treat, especially due to their location and complexity. With limited access to laboratory facilities , beginner researchers can still contribute by using freely available computational tools. In this mini review, I explore the natural compound Licochalcone A , a flavonoid from licorice root and its interaction with Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR) , a key protein in brain tumor proliferation. Using basic computational tools like SwissADME for drug likeness analysis and CB-Dock2 for molecular docking, this self-guided study aims to highlight the compound's druggability and binding affinity with EGFR. The review also reflects on the learning process of a student entering the field of medicinal chemistry with minimal lab access but high motivation to contribute to affordable cancer therapies.

INTRODUCTION : Brain tumors are present major therapeutic challenges due to their complexity, recurrence , and resistance to conventional treatment . Among several molecular targets, EGFR is notably overexpressed in various cancers, including glioblastoma. Natural compounds like Licochalcone A are gaining attention for their anti-cancerous activities and fewer side effects . This paper explores the potential of Licochalcone A as an EGFR inhibitor using basic structure based virtual screening methods . The aim to build foundational skills in computational drug discovery while investigating real world investigations.

METHODS :

1. LIGAND PREPARATION:

- COMPOUND – Licochalcone A
- SOURCE – Pubchem
- SMILES – Retrieved and visualized
- DRUG LIKENESS – Evaluated using SwissADME
 - Lipinski's rule of five
 - Water solubility
 - Synthetic accessibility

2. PROTEIN PREPARATION:

- TARGET - EGFR (2Z4Q)
- Downloaded from RCSB PDB
- Cleaned using PyMOL (chains, water, and heteroatoms removed)

3. DOCKING:

- TOOL – CB-Dock 2 (Blind Docking approach)
- OUTPUT- Top binding cavities identified , vina score generated
- BEST Vina Score : -6.7 kcal/mol at C3 pocket

4. RESULTS:

PARAMETER	RESULT
Lipinski violation	0
Synthetic accessibility	3.23
Water solubility	Moderately soluble
Top vina score	-6.7 kcal/mol at C3 pocket
Pocket volume	923Å ³

5. INTERPRETATION :

- The docking score suggests favorable binding with EGFR
- Drug likeness profile supports further investigation

6. DISCUSSION :

Although this research is in a beginner stage, the results align with previous studies showing EGFR as a viable anticancer target. Licochalcone A demonstrates both good drug like properties and docking affinity, justifying future experimental validation.

This work is a part of larger goal to learn computational tools in absence of lab access, aiming to contribute to low cost drug development in oncology.

7. CONCLUSION :

The study provides a basic yet promising insight into the use of natural compounds like Licochalcone A in cancer therapy. With continued learning and mentorship, such self-guided projects can evolve into impactful research contributions.

8. AUTHOR STATEMENT:

This mini review is part of a self-guided learning initiative by a postgraduate student (Priyanjali Singh) with no access to experimental labs, intending to build skills in structure-based drug design and contribute to affordable cancer research.

9. REFERENCES:

1. SwissADME: <http://www.swissadme.ch/>
2. CB-Dock2: <https://cadd.labshare.cn/cb-dock2/php/blinddock.php>
3. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S037887411631666X>
4. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1005824802617>